

Search protocols

1. Pubmed

Search: ("Breast Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "breast cancer" OR "breast neoplasm*") AND ("Radiotherapy"[Mesh] OR Radiotherapy OR "adjuvant radiotherapy") AND ("Patient Education as Topic"[Mesh] OR "patient education "OR "educational need*" OR "informational need*" OR knowledge) AND ("Perception"[Mesh] OR perception* OR attitude* OR awareness) AND ("Female"[Mesh] OR Female* OR women) Filters: from 2009 - 2024

((("Breast Neoplasms"[MeSH Terms] OR "breast cancer"[All Fields] OR "breast neoplasm*"[All Fields]) AND ("Radiotherapy"[MeSH Terms] OR ("Radiotherapy"[MeSH Terms] OR "Radiotherapy"[All Fields] OR "radiotherapies"[All Fields] OR "Radiotherapy"[MeSH Subheading] OR "radiotherapy s"[All Fields]) OR "adjuvant radiotherapy"[All Fields]) AND ("Patient Education as Topic"[MeSH Terms] OR "patient education"[All Fields] OR "educational need*"[All Fields] OR "informational need*"[All Fields] OR ("knowledge"[MeSH Terms] OR "knowledge"[All Fields] OR "knowledge s"[All Fields] OR "knowledgeability"[All Fields] OR "knowledgeable"[All Fields] OR "knowledgeably"[All Fields] OR "knowledges"[All Fields])) AND ("Perception"[MeSH Terms] OR "perception*"[All Fields] OR "attitude*"[All Fields] OR ("awareness"[MeSH Terms] OR "awareness"[All Fields] OR "aware"[All Fields] OR "awarenesses"[All Fields])) AND ("Female"[MeSH Terms] OR "female*"[All Fields] OR ("womans"[All Fields] OR "women"[MeSH Terms] OR "women"[All Fields] OR "woman"[All Fields] OR "women s"[All Fields] OR "womens"[All Fields]))) AND (2009:2024[pdat])

Translations

Radiotherapy: "radiotherapy"[MeSH Terms] OR "radiotherapy"[All Fields] OR "radiotherapies"[All Fields] OR "radiotherapy"[Subheading] OR "radiotherapy's"[All Fields]

knowledge: "knowledge"[MeSH Terms] OR "knowledge"[All Fields] OR "knowledge's"[All Fields] OR "knowledgeability"[All Fields] OR "knowledgeable"[All Fields] OR "knowledgeably"[All Fields] OR "knowledges"[All Fields]

awareness: "awareness"[MeSH Terms] OR "awareness"[All Fields] OR "aware"[All Fields] OR "awarenesses"[All Fields]

women: "womans"[All Fields] OR "women"[MeSH Terms] OR "women"[All Fields] OR "woman"[All Fields] OR "women's"[All Fields] OR "womens"[All Fields]

2. SCOPUS

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (("breast cancer" OR "breast neoplasm*")) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ((radiotherapy OR "adjuvant radiotherapy")) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (("patient education " OR "educational need*" OR "informational need*" OR knowledge)) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (("perception*" OR "attitude*" OR "awareness*")) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ((female* OR women))) AND PUBYEAR > 2008 AND PUBYEAR < 2025

3. CINAHL

(breast cancer or breast neoplasm or breast carcinoma or breast tumor) AND (radiotherapy OR adjuvant radiotherapy) AND (Patient education OR Educational need OR Informational need* OR Expectation* OR Knowledge) AND (Perception* OR Attitude* OR Awareness) AND (woman or women or female or females)

Limiters: - Publication Date: 20090101-20241231

Search modes: Proximity

4. Web of Science

“breast cancer” OR “breast neoplasm*” **(Topic) and** Radiotherapy OR “adjuvant radiotherapy” **(Topic) and** "patient education“ OR “educational need*” OR “informational need*” OR knowledge **(Topic) and** perception* OR awareness **(Topic)and** Female* OR women **(Topic) and** 2009-2024 **(Publication Years)**